

Workshop

Ethics in Action - Annual Workshop for Transplant Coordinators

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The Network and Alliance of Transplant Coordinators (NATCO) successfully hosted its 17th Annual Conference on October 19-20, 2024, at the KD Hospital Auditorium in Ahmedabad. The two-day event, graciously hosted by KD Hospital, brought together experts, doctors, and transplant coordinators under the theme "Ethics in Action," focusing on ethical practices and the indispensable role of transplant coordinators in advancing organ donation in India.

The conference began with an inaugural ceremony led by Dr. Sunil Shroff, Managing Trustee of MOHAN Foundation, and Dr. Rakesh Joshi, Medical Superintendent of Civil Hospital, Ahmedabad. Both dignitaries emphasized the significance of ethical considerations in organ donation, setting the tone for the event. A "Handbook for Registering Hospitals as Transplant Centers," developed by NATCO was released during the inaugural ceremony.

The first day featured discussions on successful deceased organ donation programs in Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, and Manipur, as well as innovative approaches to post-transplant patient care. A session on challenges and achievements faced by NGOs welcomed valuable input from organizations such as MF Jaipur Citizen Forum, Muskaan, ORGAN India, Shatayu, Shine India, Rotary Club of Organ Donation, Eye Bank Society of Rajasthan, and Bengal Organ Donation Society.

The highlight was the **Swami Narayan Memorial Oration** by **Padmashree awardee Dr. Janak Palta McGilligan**, whose narrative underscored the societal and ethical impact of organ donation.

The screening of *God Vulture and Human*, a documentary by Rishiraj Agarwal and co-produced by Prof. Rajesh Chandwani, left a profound impact. It shed light on the human and ethical aspects of organ donation, emphasizing the critical role of transplant

coordinators. Delegates also participated in a free paper session, presenting research and field experiences evaluated by a panel of esteemed judges.

On the second day, discussions addressed organ donation trends at government hospitals, including insights from AIIMS Raipur, AIIMS Bhubaneswar, JNIMS Imphal, and GMC Nagpur. Other topics included leveraging government schemes, improving documentation skills, and exploring crowdfunding for underprivileged patients. These sessions offered practical strategies to empower transplant coordinators and enhance their effectiveness.

The Conference provided a valuable platform for knowledge sharing, professional growth, and networking. It reaffirmed the organization's unwavering commitment to ethical practices and the advancement of transplantation efforts in India. By fostering dialogue, practical learning, and sharing insights into the challenges and rewards of their work, the conference continues to inspire and empower transplant coordinators, strengthening the country's transplantation ecosystem.

"Congratulations on organizing and successfully executing the 17th Annual NATCO Conference. Every component was well thought out. Although I am not a transplant coordinator, I gained a great deal of knowledge over the past two days and had the opportunity to meet many wonderful and inspiring individuals." - Ms. Hemali Ajmera

"The hallmark of exceptional transplant programs globally is the presence of outstanding transplant coordinators. This conference truly showcased their dedication and expertise, reaffirming the importance of their role in India's expanding transplantation programs." - Mr. Atul Agnihotri

"It was an honour to chair a session and engage with esteemed colleagues dedicated to advancing deceased organ donation. The collaborative environment and insights gained were invaluable, and I deeply appreciate the warm hospitality extended by NATCO." - Dr. Chintan Chaudhari

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